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Preprint · September 2019

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34948.88967

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Holomorphic differential forms of complex manifolds on commutative Banach algebras and a few related problems

Hiroki Yagisita (Kyoto Sangyo University)

Abstract:

Let A be a commutative Banach algebra. Let M be a complex manifold on A (an A -manifold). Then, we define an A -holomorphic vector bundle $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ on M . For an open set U of M , ω is said to be an A -holomorphic differential k -form on U , if ω is an A -holomorphic section of $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ on U . So, if the set of all A -holomorphic differential k -forms on U is denoted by $\Omega_M^k(U)$, then $\{\Omega_M^k(U)\}_U$ is a sheaf of modules on the structure sheaf O_M of the A -manifold M and the cohomology group $H^l(M, \Omega_M^k)$ with the coefficient sheaf $\{\Omega_M^k(U)\}_U$ is an $O_M(M)$ -module and therefore, in particular, an A -module. There is no new thing in our definition of a holomorphic differential form. However, this is necessary to get the cohomology group $H^l(M, \Omega_M^k)$ as an A -module.

Furthermore, we try to define the structure sheaf of a manifold that is locally a continuous family of \mathbb{C} -manifolds (and also the one of an analytic family). Directing attention to a finite family of \mathbb{C} -manifolds, we mentioned the possibility that Dolbeault theorem holds for a continuous sum of \mathbb{C} -manifolds. Also, we state a few related problems. One of them is the following. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, does there exist a \mathbb{C}^n -manifold N such that (1) for any \mathbb{C} -manifolds M_1, M_2, \dots, M_{n-1} and M_n , N can not be embedded in the direct product $M_1 \times M_2 \times \dots \times M_{n-1} \times M_n$ as a \mathbb{C}^n -submanifold but (2) there exists $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that N can be embedded in the k -dimensional Euclidean \mathbb{R}^n -space $(\mathbb{R}^k)^n$ as an \mathbb{R}^n -submanifold? So, we propose something that is likely to be a candidate for such a \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold N .

Keywords: additive Cousin problem, foliation, foliated manifold, K-group, Riemann-Roch theorem, Gelfand representation, von Neumann algebra, Radon measure, L^∞ space, coherent analytic sheaf, domain of holomorphy, holomorphically convex, $\bar{\partial}$ equation, Levi problem, pseudoconvex manifold, Stein manifold, Kahler manifold, immersion, Kodaira embedding theorem, Kodaira vanishing theorem, harmonic integral, relative de Rham resolution, Weierstrass preparation theorem, projective algebraic variety, Chow's theorem, Serre's GAGA, vector sheaf, non-Hausdorff manifold.

1 Definitions and problems

From §2 of [8], we follow some terms (e.g., commutative Banach algebra, Banach A -module, etc.).

Let A be a commutative Banach algebra and be fixed.

Definition 1 (Topological module) :

X is said to be a topological A -module, if X is an A -module, it is a topological \mathbb{C} -linear space,

$$(c1_A)u = cu \quad (c \in \mathbb{C}, u \in X)$$

holds and the map

$$(a, u) \in A \times X \quad \mapsto \quad au \in X$$

is continuous.

Remark :

If one is a Banach A -module, then it is a topological A -module. —

Definition 2 (Linear mapping) :

Let X and Y be A -modules. A mapping $F : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be A -linear, if it satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} F(u + v) &= F(u) + F(v) \quad (u, v \in X), \\ F(fu) &= fF(u) \quad (f \in A, u \in X). \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3 (Continuous multilinear mapping) :

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k and Y be topological A -modules. A map f from $X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_k$ to Y is said to be (A, k) -linear, if f is A -linear with respect to each variable $x_i \in X_i$. Let $L_A(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k; Y)$ denote the set of all continuous (A, k) -linear mappings from $X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_k$ to Y . $L_A(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k; Y)$ is an A -module.

Remark : If one is (A, k) -linear, then it is (\mathbb{C}, k) -linear. —

Definition 4 (Norm of a multilinear mapping) :

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k and Y be Banach A -modules. For an (A, k) -linear mapping f from $X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_k$ to Y , let

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\| &:= \sup \{ \|f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)\|_Y \mid \\ &\|x_1\|_{X_1} = \|x_2\|_{X_2} = \dots = \|x_k\|_{X_k} = 1 \}. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 5 :

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k and Y be Banach A -modules. Then, for any (A, k) -linear mapping f from $X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_k$ to Y , f is continuous if and only if $\|f\| < +\infty$ holds. $L_A(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k; Y)$ is a Banach A -module.

Proof : It is easy. ■

Definition 6 (Continuous antisymmetric form) :

Let X be a topological A -module. A mapping f from X^k to A is said to be an (A, k) -linear form of X , if f is (A, k) -linear. An (A, k) -linear form f of X is said to be antisymmetric, if for any permutation σ , $f(x_{\sigma(1)}, x_{\sigma(2)}, \dots, x_{\sigma(k)}) = \text{sgn}(\sigma) \cdot f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)$ holds. Let $A_A^k(X)$ denote the set of all continuous antisymmetric (A, k) -linear forms of X . $A_A^k(X)$ is an A -submodule of $L_A(X, X, \dots, X; A)$.

Lemma 7 :

Let X be a Banach A -module. Then, $A_A^k(X)$ is a Banach A -submodule of $L_A(X, X, \dots, X; A)$.

Proof : It is easy. ■

Definition 8 (Pull back) :

Let X_1 and X_2 be topological A -modules. For a map F from X_1 to X_2 and a map f from X_2^k to A , define a map $F^*(f)$ from X_1^k to A by

$$(F^*(f))(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k) := f(F(x_1), F(x_2), \dots, F(x_k)).$$

If $F \in L_A(X_1; X_2)$ and $f \in A_A^k(X_2)$ hold, then $F^*(f) \in A_A^k(X_1)$ holds. —

Lemma 9 :

Let X_1 and X_2 be topological A -modules. Suppose that F is a bijection from X_1 to X_2 . Suppose that F and F^{-1} are continuous and A -linear. Then, $F^*_{\downarrow A_A^k(X_2)}$ is a bijection to $A_A^k(X_1)$. $F^*_{\downarrow A_A^k(X_2)}$ and $F^*_{\downarrow A_A^k(X_2)}^{-1}$ are A -linear. Further, if X_1 and X_2 are Banach A -modules, then $F^*_{\downarrow A_A^k(X_2)}$ and $F^*_{\downarrow A_A^k(X_2)}^{-1}$ are continuous.

Proof : It is easy. ■

Definition 10 (Banach-like module) :

X is said to be a Banach-like A -module, if X is a topological A -module and there exist a Banach A -module Y and a bijection F from X to Y such that F and F^{-1} are continuous and A -linear. —

Lemma 11 :

Let X be a Banach-like A -module. Then, $A_A^k(X)$ is a Banach-like A -module.

Proof : It follows from Lemmas 7 and 9. ■

Definition 12 (Differentiable mapping) :

Let X and Y be Banach A -modules. Let f be a mapping from an open set U of X to Y . f is said to be A -differentiable (on U), if f is Frechet differentiable and for any $p \in U$, the Frechet derivative $(Df)_p$ is A -linear. —

Definition 13 (Manifold on a commutative Banach algebra) :

Let M be a Hausdorff space. Let S be a set. M is said to be an A -manifold with the system S of coordinate neighborhoods, if the followings hold.

For any $\varphi \in S$, there exists a Banach A -module X such that φ is a homeomorphism from an open set of M to an open set of X . For any $p \in M$, there exists $\varphi \in S$ such that p belongs to the domain of φ . For any $\varphi_1, \varphi_2 \in S$, the coordinate transformation

$$\varphi_2 \circ \varphi_1^{-1} : \varphi_1(U_1 \cap U_2) \rightarrow \varphi_2(U_1 \cap U_2)$$

is A -differentiable. Here, U_1 and U_2 are the domains of φ_1 and φ_2 , respectively. —

Let M be an A -manifold with the system S of coordinate neighborhoods and be fixed. For $\varphi \in S$, we denote the domain of φ by U_φ and the Banach A -module such that $\varphi(U_\varphi)$ is an open set of it by X_φ . For $p \in M$, we denote the set of all $\varphi \in S$ such that $p \in U_\varphi$ holds by S_p .

Definition 14 (Tangent space) :

Let $p \in M$. As $\dot{p}_1 \sim \dot{p}_2$ indicates that there exist $\varphi_1, \varphi_2 \in S_p$ such that $\dot{p}_2 = (D(\varphi_2 \circ \varphi_1^{-1}))_{\varphi_1(p)}(\dot{p}_1)$ holds, \sim is an equivalence relation of $\cup_{\varphi \in S_p} X_\varphi$. Let $T_p(M)$ denote the quotient set $(\cup_{\varphi \in S_p} X_\varphi) / \sim$. The tangent space $T_p(M)$ is a Banach-like A -module. —

Definition 15 (Cotangent exterior space) :

Let $p \in M$. Let $(\wedge^k T^*)_p(M)$ denote $A_A^k(T_p(M))$. The cotangent exterior space $(\wedge^k T^*)_p(M)$ is a Banach-like A -module. —

Definition 16 (Holomorphic mapping between complex manifolds on a commutative Banach algebra) :

Let M_1 be an A -manifold with a system S_1 of coordinate neighborhoods. Let M_2 be an A -manifold with a system S_2 of coordinate neighborhoods. Let $f : M_1 \rightarrow M_2$ be a continuous mapping. f is said to be A -holomorphic, if for any $\varphi_1 \in S_1$ and $\varphi_2 \in S_2$, the mapping

$$\varphi_2 \circ f \circ \varphi_1^{-1} : \varphi_1(U_1 \cap f^{-1}(U_2)) \rightarrow X_2$$

is A -differentiable. Here, φ_1 is a mapping from U_1 to a Banach A -module X_1 and φ_2 is a mapping from U_2 to a Banach A -module X_2 .

Remark : Let f be a map from an open set of a Banach A -module to a Banach A -module. Then, f is A -holomorphic if and only if f is A -differentiable. —

Definition 17 (Finite direct product of Banach modules) :

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{k-1} and X_k be Banach A -modules. Let

$$\|(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)\| := \max_l \|x_l\|_{X_l}$$

$$(x_1 \in X_1, x_2 \in X_2, \dots, x_k \in X_k).$$

The finite direct product $X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_k$ is a Banach A -module.

Definition 18 (Holomorphic vector bundle on a complex manifold on a commutative Banach algebra) :

$E := (E, M, \pi, \{(U_\lambda, X_\lambda, \varphi_\lambda)\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda})$ is said to be an A -holomorphic vector bundle (on M), if it satisfies the followings.

E and M are A -manifolds. π is an A -holomorphic surjection from E to M . Each U_λ is an open set of M . $M = \cup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} U_\lambda$ holds. Each φ_λ is a map from $\pi^{-1}(U_\lambda)$ to a Banach A -module X_λ . For $\lambda \in \Lambda$, let

$$\pi|_\lambda := \pi|_{\pi^{-1}(U_\lambda)}.$$

Each map

$$(\varphi_\lambda, \pi|_\lambda) : \pi^{-1}(U_\lambda) \rightarrow X_\lambda \times U_\lambda$$

is an A -biholomorphic map. For $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and $p \in U_\lambda$, let

$$\varphi_\lambda|_p := \varphi_\lambda|_{\pi^{-1}(\{p\})}.$$

For any $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \Lambda$ and $p \in U_{\lambda_1} \cap U_{\lambda_2}$, the coordinate transformation

$$\varphi_{\lambda_2}|_p \circ \varphi_{\lambda_1}|_p^{-1} : X_{\lambda_1} \rightarrow X_{\lambda_2}$$

is A -linear. —

Definition 19 (Tangent bundle) : —

Let $T(M)$ denote $\cup_{p \in M} T_p(M)$. —

Proposition 20 :

The tangent bundle $T(M) \rightarrow M$ is an A -holomorphic vector bundle.

Proof : It is a corollary of Proposition 34 in Section 2. ■

Definition 21 (Cotangent exterior bundle) :

Let $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ denote $\cup_{p \in M} (\wedge^k T^*)_p(M)$. —

Proposition 22 :

The cotangent exterior bundle $(\wedge^k T^*)(M) \rightarrow M$ is an A -holomorphic vector bundle.

Proof : It is a corollary of Proposition 38 in Section 2. ■

Theorem 23 (Probably well-known) :

Let $A = \mathbb{C}$. Let M be an n -dimensional complex manifold. For an open set U of M , the set of all holomorphic sections of $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ on U is denoted by $\Omega_M^k(U)$. Then, the sheaf $\{\Omega_M^k(U)\}_U$ on M is isomorphic to the sheaf of germs of holomorphic differential k -forms on M as a sheaf of modules on the sheaf O_M of germs of holomorphic functions on M .

Proof : As we define the correspondence F^k by

$$\begin{aligned}
 F^1(dz^i) : \quad & \sum_{j=1}^n z^j \frac{\partial}{\partial z^j} \in T_p(M) \quad \mapsto \quad z^i \in \mathbb{C} \\
 & (z = (z^1, z^2, \dots, z^n) \in \mathbb{C}^n), \\
 & F^k(dz^{i_1} \wedge dz^{i_2} \wedge \dots \wedge dz^{i_k}) \\
 := \quad & \sum_{\sigma \in S_k} \text{sgn}(\sigma) F^1(dz^{i_{\sigma(1)}}) \otimes F^1(dz^{i_{\sigma(2)}}) \otimes \dots \otimes F^1(dz^{i_{\sigma(k)}}),
 \end{aligned}$$

it is a somewhat difficult exercise of linear algebras. ■

The sheaf of germs of A -valued A -holomorphic mappings on M is denoted by O_M . From the above, we get the following definition.

Definition 24 (Holomorphic differential form of a complex manifold on a commutative Banach algebra) :

Let U be an open set of M . ω is said to be an A -holomorphic differential k -form on U , if it is an A -holomorphic section of $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ on U . Let $\Omega_M^k(U)$ denote the set of all A -holomorphic differential k -forms on U . Then, $\{\Omega_M^k(U)\}_U$ is a sheaf of modules on the sheaf O_M of germs of A -valued A -holomorphic mappings on M . The cohomology group $H^l(M, \Omega_M^k)$ with the coefficient sheaf $\{\Omega_M^k(U)\}_U$ is an $O_M(M)$ -module and, in particular, an A -module.

Remark :

In the coefficient sheaf $\{\Omega_M^k(U)\}_U$, U may be limited only to all open sets of M in an appropriate (weak) topology depending on the problem. —

Problem 25 :

Let N be a compact continuous family of connected n -dimensional \mathbb{C} -manifolds on a compact Hausdorff space X . Let $\Gamma(N)$ denote the set of all continuous sections of N on X . Then, $\Gamma(N)$ is a $C(X)$ -manifold. (see [8].) So, if M is an open set of $\Gamma(N)$, then the cohomology group $H^l(M, \Omega_M^k)$ is an $O_M(M)$ -module and, in particular, a $C(X)$ -module.

(1) Let M be a connected component of $\Gamma(N)$. Is $O_M(M) = C(X)$? Seek more specific indications of the sheaf Ω_M^k and the cohomology group $H^l(M, \Omega_M^k)$. When is $H^l(M, \Omega_M^k)$ a finitely generated projective $C(X)$ -module? Define the Euler characteristic $\chi(M, O_M) = \sum_l (-1)^l [H^l(M, O_M)] \in K(X) = K(C(X))$ and seek its Riemann-Roch indication.

(2) Let M_1 and M_2 be connected components of $\Gamma(N)$. Then, when are $H^l(M_1, \Omega_{M_1}^k)$ and $H^l(M_2, \Omega_{M_2}^k)$ isomorphic as $C(X)$ -modules?

Problem 26 :

(1) Define a differential (p, q) -form and the Dolbeault operator $\bar{\partial}$ of an A -manifold. (For the case of an infinite-dimensional \mathbb{C} -manifold, see [3].)

(2) Let D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{n-1} and D_n be open disks of A . Then, is for any $l \geq 1$, $H^l(D_1 \times D_2 \times \dots \times D_n, O_{D_1 \times D_2 \times \dots \times D_n}) = 0$?

(3) Let U be a connected open set of A^n . Let F be an O_U -module. Then, when is for any $l \geq 1$, $H^l(U, F) = 0$? For example, when $A = C(\{0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1\}) = \mathbb{C}^m$ holds, define that a connected open set U of \mathbb{C}^{mn} is \mathbb{C}^m -Stein. Also, define a \mathbb{C}^m -coherent analytic sheaf on U .

(4) Let M be an A -real analytic manifold. Then, define the sheaf of germs of A -real valued A -real continuous mappings on M and the one of A -real valued A -real hyperfunctions on M .

Remark :

Related to some of Problems 25 and 26, see Appendix 1. Perhaps, it may be meaningful to have E_k as the sheaf of germs of C^∞ -functions on \mathbb{R}^k in $0 \rightarrow E_{n,x} \times \{0_y\} \rightarrow E_{n,x} \times E_{m,y} \rightarrow \{0_x\} \times E_{m,y} \rightarrow 0$. Apparently, a resolution like Dolbeault ones and de Rham ones intertwined seems to be a fine one of the structure sheaf of a \mathbb{C}^m -manifold.

In Appendix 2, we tried to define an analog of singular homology theory for a *continuous family of topological spaces*. In Appendix 3, we mentioned the possibility that Dolbeault theorem holds for a *continuous sum of \mathbb{C} -manifolds*. In Appendix 4, we try to define the structure sheaf of a manifold that is *locally* a continuous family of \mathbb{C} -manifolds (and also the one of an analytic family). —

Additional Problem :

Consider the following 1-dimensional \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold N . It consists of four coordinate neighborhoods $\varphi_k : W_k \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^2$ ($k = 1, 2, 3, 4$). That is,

$$N = \cup_{k=1}^4 W_k.$$

Let

$$\varphi_1(W_1) := \mathbb{C} \times \{z_2 \in \mathbb{C} \mid \text{Im } z_2 > 0\},$$

$$\varphi_2(W_2) := \mathbb{C} \times \{z_2 \in \mathbb{C} \mid \text{Im } z_2 < 0\},$$

$$\varphi_3(W_3) := \{z_1 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_1| < 1\} \times \mathbb{C},$$

$$\varphi_4(W_4) := \{z_1 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_1| < 1\} \times \mathbb{C}.$$

Let $W_1 \cap W_2 = \emptyset$ and $W_3 \cap W_4 = \emptyset$. Let c_1 and c_2 be real numbers such that

$$0 < c_1 < c_2 < +\infty$$

holds. Let

$$\varphi_3(W_1 \cap W_3) = \{z_1 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_1| < 1\} \times \{z_2 \in \mathbb{C} \mid \text{Im } z_2 > +c_1\},$$

$$(\varphi_1 \circ (\varphi_3^{-1}))(z_1, z_2) = (z_1 + (+2), z_2 + (-c_1\sqrt{-1})).$$

Let

$$\varphi_4(W_1 \cap W_4) = \{z_1 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_1| < 1\} \times \{z_2 \in \mathbb{C} \mid \text{Im } z_2 > +c_2\},$$

$$(\varphi_1 \circ (\varphi_4^{-1}))(z_1, z_2) = (z_1 + (-2), z_2 + (-c_2\sqrt{-1})).$$

Let

$$\varphi_3(W_2 \cap W_3) = \{z_1 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_1| < 1\} \times \{z_2 \in \mathbb{C} \mid \text{Im } z_2 < -c_1\},$$

$$(\varphi_2 \circ (\varphi_3^{-1}))(z_1, z_2) = (z_1 + (+2), z_2 + (+c_1\sqrt{-1})).$$

Let

$$\varphi_4(W_2 \cap W_4) = \{z_1 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_1| < 1\} \times \{z_2 \in \mathbb{C} \mid \text{Im } z_2 < -c_2\},$$

$$(\varphi_2 \circ (\varphi_4^{-1}))(z_1, z_2) = (z_1 + (-2), z_2 + (+c_2\sqrt{-1})).$$

Then, answer the following question. Do \mathbb{C} -manifolds M_1 and M_2 exist such that N is embedded in $M_1 \times M_2$ as a \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold? (If we allow that M_1 and M_2 are *not Hausdorff*, what about?) —

2 Proof of Propositions 20 and 22

Proposition 27 :

Let f be an A -differentiable mapping from an open set U of a Banach A -module X to a Banach A -module Y . Then, the mapping

$$(\dot{z}, z) \in X \times U \quad \mapsto \quad (Df)_z(\dot{z}) \in Y$$

is A -differentiable.

Proof : Let $F(\dot{z}, z) := (Df)_z(\dot{z})$. Let $(\dot{z}_0, z_0) \in X \times U$. Then, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$\|z - z_0\|_X < \varepsilon \quad \implies \quad z \in U$$

holds. Further, there exists $C > 0$ such that

$$\|\dot{z}_0\|_X < \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon C$$

holds. Because f is \mathbb{C} -differentiable on U ,

$$\begin{aligned} \|z - z_0\|_X < \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon, \quad \|\dot{z}\|_X < \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon C \\ \implies \\ F(\dot{z}, z) &= C (Df)_z\left(\frac{1}{C}\dot{z}\right) = C \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} f\left(z + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{C}\dot{z}\right) d\theta \end{aligned}$$

holds. Hence, for any $(\dot{h}, h) \in X^2$,

$$(DF)_{(\dot{z}_0, z_0)}(\dot{h}, h) = C \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} (Df)_{z_0 + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{C}\dot{z}_0}(h + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{C}\dot{h}) d\theta$$

holds. Because $(Df)_z$ is A -linear, for any $a \in A$ and $(\dot{h}, h) \in X^2$,

$$\begin{aligned} &(DF)_{(\dot{z}_0, z_0)}(a(\dot{h}, h)) \\ &= C \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} (Df)_{z_0 + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{C}\dot{z}_0}(ah + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{C}a\dot{h}) d\theta \\ &= a C \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} (Df)_{z_0 + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{C}\dot{z}_0}(h + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{C}\dot{h}) d\theta \\ &= a (DF)_{(\dot{z}_0, z_0)}(\dot{h}, h) \end{aligned}$$

holds. ■

Proposition 28 :

Let f be an A -differentiable mapping from an open set U of a Banach A -module X to a Banach A -module Y . Then, the mapping

$$z \in U \quad \mapsto \quad (Df)_z \in L_A(X; Y)$$

is A -differentiable.

Proof : Let $G(z) := (Df)_z$. Let $z_0 \in U$. Then, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$\|z - z_0\|_X < \varepsilon \quad \implies \quad z \in U$$

holds. Because f is \mathbb{C} -differentiable on U , for any $h, \dot{z}_0 \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned} & ((DG)_{z_0}(h))(\dot{z}_0) \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X\right) \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{(Df)_{z_0+th} \left(\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0\right) - (Df)_{z_0} \left(\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0\right)}{t} \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X\right) \frac{1}{2\pi} \\ & \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{f\left(z_0 + th\right) + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0 - f\left(z_0 + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0\right)}{t} d\theta \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X\right) \frac{1}{2\pi} \\ & \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{f\left(z_0 + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0 + th\right) - f\left(z_0 + e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0\right)}{t} d\theta \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X\right) \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} (Df)_{z_0+e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0}(h) d\theta \end{aligned}$$

holds. Hence, because $(Df)_z$ is A -linear, for any $a \in A$ and $h, \dot{z}_0 \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned} & ((DG)_{z_0}(ah))(\dot{z}_0) \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X\right) \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} (Df)_{z_0+e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0}(ah) d\theta \\ &= a \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X\right) \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-\sqrt{-1}\theta} (Df)_{z_0+e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \|\dot{z}_0\|_X} \dot{z}_0}(h) d\theta \\ &= (a(DG)_{z_0}(h))(\dot{z}_0) \end{aligned}$$

holds. ■

Lemma 29 :

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k and Y be Banach A -modules. Let $f \in L_A(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k; Y)$. Then, f is A -differentiable.

Proof : Let $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k) \in X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_k$. Then, the map

$$\begin{aligned} & (h_1, h_2, \dots, h_k) \in X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_k \\ \mapsto & f(h_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{k-1}, x_k) + f(x_1, h_2, x_3, \dots, x_{k-1}, x_k) \\ & + \dots + f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{k-1}, h_k) \in Y \end{aligned}$$

is A -linear, continuous and the Frechet derivative of f at x . ■

Lemma 30 :

Let X_1 and X_2 be Banach A -modules. Then, the map

$$(F, f) \in L_A(X_1; X_2) \times A_A^k(X_2) \quad \mapsto \quad F^*(f) \in A_A^k(X_1)$$

is A -differentiable.

Proof : The map

$$\begin{aligned} & (F_1, F_2, \dots, F_k, f) \in (L_A(X_1; X_2))^k \times L_A(X_2, X_2, \dots, X_2; A) \\ \mapsto & (F_1, F_2, \dots, F_k)^*(f) \in L_A(X_1, X_1, \dots, X_1; A) \end{aligned}$$

defined by

$$((F_1, F_2, \dots, F_k)^*(f))(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k) := f(F_1(x_1), F_2(x_2), \dots, F_k(x_k))$$

is continuous and $(A, k+1)$ -linear and so, from Lemma 29, A -differentiable. From $F^*(f) = (F, F, \dots, F)^*(f)$, it follows. ■

Definition 31 (Tangent trivialization neighborhood) :

Let $\varphi \in S$. Let $(\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi) : \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi) \rightarrow X_\varphi \times U_\varphi$ denote the local trivialization coordinate system of $T(M)$ corresponding to φ . That is, for any $\dot{p} \in \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi)$,

$$\dot{p} = (\{ (D(\psi \circ \varphi^{-1}))_{\varphi(\pi(\dot{p}))}(\varphi_T(\dot{p})) \}_{\psi \in S_{\pi(\dot{p})}}, \pi(\dot{p}))$$

holds. —

Definition 32 (Tangent open base) :

Let B_T denote the set of all sets W such that there exist $\varphi \in S$, an open set G of X_φ and an open set V of U_φ such that $W = (\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)^{-1}(G \times V)$ holds. —

Lemma 33 :

B_T is an open base of $T(M)$. By B_T , $T(M)$ is a Hausdorff space. For any $\varphi \in S$, the map

$$(\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi) : \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi) \rightarrow X_\varphi \times U_\varphi$$

is a homeomorphism.

Proof :

1°: Let $\dot{p} \in T(M)$. Then, there exists $\varphi \in S$ such that $\pi(\dot{p}) \in U_\varphi$ holds. $\dot{p} \in \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi)$ and $(\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)(\dot{p}) \in X_\varphi \times U_\varphi$ hold. So, $\dot{p} \in (\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)^{-1}(X_\varphi \times U_\varphi)$ holds.

2°: Let $\varphi_1 \in S$ and $\varphi_2 \in S$. Let G_1 be an open set of X_{φ_1} , G_2 be an open set of X_{φ_2} , V_1 be an open set of U_{φ_1} and V_2 be an open set of U_{φ_2} . Let $\dot{p} \in (\varphi_{1T}, \pi|_{\varphi_1})^{-1}(G_1 \times V_1)$ and $\dot{p} \in (\varphi_{2T}, \pi|_{\varphi_2})^{-1}(G_2 \times V_2)$. Then,

$$(D(\varphi_2 \circ \varphi_1^{-1}))_{\varphi_1(\pi(\dot{p}))}(\varphi_{1T}(\dot{p})) = \varphi_{2T}(\dot{p}) \in G_2$$

holds. Hence, by $\pi(\dot{p}) \in V_2$ and Proposition 27, there exist an open set G_0 of X_{φ_1} and an open set V_0 of $U_{\varphi_1} \cap U_{\varphi_2}$ such that $(\varphi_{1T}(\dot{p}), \pi(\dot{p})) \in G_0 \times V_0$ and

$$(\dot{z}, q) \in G_0 \times V_0 \implies ((D(\varphi_2 \circ \varphi_1^{-1}))_{\varphi_1(q)}(\dot{z}), q) \in G_2 \times V_2$$

hold. Then, $G_0 \cap G_1$ is an open set of X_{φ_1} , $V_0 \cap V_1$ is an open set of U_{φ_1} and

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p} &\in (\varphi_{1T}, \pi|_{\varphi_1})^{-1}((G_0 \cap G_1) \times (V_0 \cap V_1)) \\ &\subset ((\varphi_{1T}, \pi|_{\varphi_1})^{-1}(G_1 \times V_1)) \cap ((\varphi_{2T}, \pi|_{\varphi_2})^{-1}(G_2 \times V_2)) \end{aligned}$$

holds.

3°: From 1° and 2°, B_T is an open base. It is easy to see that $T(M)$ is Hausdorff.

4°: Let $\varphi \in S$. It is easy to see that $(\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)$ is a continuous bijection. We show that $(\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)^{-1}$ is continuous. Let W be an open set of $\pi^{-1}(U_\varphi)$. Let $\dot{p} \in W$. Then, there exist $\psi \in S$, an open set G of X_ψ and an open set V of U_ψ such that

$$\dot{p} \in (\psi_T, \pi|_\psi)^{-1}(G \times V) \subset W$$

holds. Then,

$$(D(\psi \circ \varphi^{-1}))_{\varphi(\pi(\dot{p}))}(\varphi_T(\dot{p})) = \psi_T(\dot{p}) \in G$$

holds. Hence, by $\pi(\dot{p}) \in V$ and Proposition 27, there exist an open set G_0 of X_φ and an open set V_0 of $U_\varphi \cap U_\psi$ such that $(\varphi_T(\dot{p}), \pi(\dot{p})) \in G_0 \times V_0$ and

$$(\dot{z}, q) \in G_0 \times V_0 \implies ((D(\psi \circ \varphi^{-1}))_{\varphi(q)}(\dot{z}), q) \in G \times V$$

hold. Then, $G_0 \times V_0$ is an open set of $X_\varphi \times U_\varphi$ and

$$\dot{p} \in (\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)^{-1}(G_0 \times V_0) \subset (\psi_T, \pi|_\psi)^{-1}(G \times V) \subset W$$

holds. Therefore, $(\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)^{-1}$ is continuous. ■

Proposition 34 :

The Hausdorff space $T(M)$ is an A -manifold with $\{(\varphi_T, \varphi \circ \pi|_\varphi)\}_{\varphi \in S}$ as the system of coordinate neighborhoods. The A -manifold $T(M)$ is an A -holomorphic vector bundle on M with $\{(\varphi_T, \pi|_\varphi)\}_{\varphi \in S}$ as the system of local trivialization coordinate neighborhoods.

Proof : It follows from Proposition 27 and Lemma 33. ■

Definition 35 (Cotangent exterior trivialization neighborhood) :

Let $\varphi \in S$. Let $(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_\varphi) : \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi) \rightarrow A_A^k(X_\varphi) \times U_\varphi$ denote the local trivialization coordinate system of $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ corresponding to φ . That is, for any $f \in \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi)$ and $\dot{p}_1, \dot{p}_2, \dots, \dot{p}_k \in T_{\pi(f)}(M)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & f(\dot{p}_1, \dot{p}_2, \dots, \dot{p}_k) \\ &= (\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}(f))((\varphi_T|_{\pi(f)})(\dot{p}_1), (\varphi_T|_{\pi(f)})(\dot{p}_2), \dots, (\varphi_T|_{\pi(f)})(\dot{p}_k)) \end{aligned}$$

holds. Here, let $\varphi_T|_p := \varphi_T|_{T_p(M)}$ for $p \in U_\varphi$. —

Definition 36 (Cotangent exterior open base) :

Let $B_{\wedge^k T^*}$ denote the set of all sets W such that there exist $\varphi \in S$, an open set G of $A_A^k(X_\varphi)$ and an open set V of U_φ such that $W = (\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_\varphi)^{-1}(G \times V)$ holds. —

Lemma 37 :

$B_{\wedge^k T^*}$ is an open base of $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$. By $B_{\wedge^k T^*}$, $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ is a Hausdorff space. For any $\varphi \in S$, the map

$$(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_\varphi) : \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi) \rightarrow A_A^k(X_\varphi) \times U_\varphi$$

is a homeomorphism.

Proof :

1°: Let $f \in (\wedge^k T^*)(M)$. Then, there exists $\varphi \in S$ such that $\pi(f) \in U_\varphi$ holds. $f \in \pi^{-1}(U_\varphi)$ and $(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_\varphi)(f) \in A_A^k(X_\varphi) \times U_\varphi$ hold. So, $f \in (\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_\varphi)^{-1}(A_A^k(X_\varphi) \times U_\varphi)$ holds.

2°: Let $\varphi_1 \in S$ and $\varphi_2 \in S$. Let G_1 be an open set of $A_A^k(X_{\varphi_1})$, G_2 be an open set of $A_A^k(X_{\varphi_2})$, V_1 be an open set of U_{φ_1} and V_2 be an open set of U_{φ_2} . Let $f \in (\varphi_{1\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi_1})^{-1}(G_1 \times V_1)$ and $f \in (\varphi_{2\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi_2})^{-1}(G_2 \times V_2)$. Then,

$$((D(\varphi_1 \circ \varphi_2^{-1}))_{\varphi_2(\pi(f))})^*(\varphi_{1\wedge^k T^*}(f)) = \varphi_{2\wedge^k T^*}(f) \in G_2$$

holds. Hence, by $\pi(f) \in V_2$, Proposition 28 and Lemma 30, there exist an open set G_0 of $A_A^k(X_{\varphi_1})$ and an open set V_0 of $U_{\varphi_1} \cap U_{\varphi_2}$ such that $(\varphi_{1\wedge^k T^*}(f), \pi(f)) \in G_0 \times V_0$ and

$$(h, q) \in G_0 \times V_0 \implies (((D(\varphi_1 \circ \varphi_2^{-1}))_{\varphi_2(q)})^*(h), q) \in G_2 \times V_2$$

hold. Then, $G_0 \cap G_1$ is an open set of $A_A^k(X_{\varphi_1})$, $V_0 \cap V_1$ is an open set of U_{φ_1} and

$$\begin{aligned} f &\in (\varphi_{1\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi_1})^{-1}((G_0 \cap G_1) \times (V_0 \cap V_1)) \\ &\subset ((\varphi_{1\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi_1})^{-1}(G_1 \times V_1)) \cap ((\varphi_{2\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi_2})^{-1}(G_2 \times V_2)) \end{aligned}$$

holds.

3°: From 1° and 2°, $B_{\wedge^k T^*}$ is an open base. It is easy to see that $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ is Hausdorff.

4°: Let $\varphi \in S$. It is easy to see that $(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi})$ is a continuous bijection. We show that $(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi})^{-1}$ is continuous. Let W be an open set of $\pi^{-1}(U_{\varphi})$. Let $f \in W$. Then, there exist $\psi \in S$, an open set G of $A_A^k(X_{\psi})$ and an open set V of U_{ψ} such that

$$f \in (\psi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\psi})^{-1}(G \times V) \subset W$$

holds. Then,

$$((D(\varphi \circ \psi^{-1}))_{\psi(\pi(f))})^*(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}(f)) = \psi_{\wedge^k T^*}(f) \in G$$

holds. Hence, by $\pi(f) \in V$, Proposition 28 and Lemma 30, there exist an open set G_0 of $A_A^k(X_{\varphi})$ and an open set V_0 of $U_{\varphi} \cap U_{\psi}$ such that $(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}(f), \pi(f)) \in G_0 \times V_0$ and

$$(h, q) \in G_0 \times V_0 \implies (((D(\varphi \circ \psi^{-1}))_{\psi(q)})^*(h), q) \in G \times V$$

hold. Then, $G_0 \times V_0$ is an open set of $A_A^k(X_{\varphi}) \times U_{\varphi}$ and

$$f \in (\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi})^{-1}(G_0 \times V_0) \subset (\psi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\psi})^{-1}(G \times V) \subset W$$

holds. Therefore, $(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi})^{-1}$ is continuous. ■

Proposition 38 :

The Hausdorff space $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ is an A -manifold with $\{(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \varphi \circ \pi|_{\varphi})\}_{\varphi \in S}$ as the system of coordinate neighborhoods. The A -manifold $(\wedge^k T^*)(M)$ is an A -holomorphic vector bundle on M with $\{(\varphi_{\wedge^k T^*}, \pi|_{\varphi})\}_{\varphi \in S}$ as the system of local trivialization coordinate neighborhoods.

Proof : It follows from Proposition 28 and Lemmas 30, 37. ■

Acknowledgment:

This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP16K05245. ArXiv does not seem to accept frequent revisions. The revised version may have been put in “https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hiroki_Yagisita”.

Appendix

1 : Let X be a compact Hausdorff space. Let U be a convex open set of \mathbb{R}^n . Let F be a C^1 -map from $C(X; U)$ to $C(X; \mathbb{R})$. Suppose that for any $u \in C(X; U)$, the Frechet derivative $F'(u)$ of F at u is $C(X; \mathbb{R})$ -linear. Then, for any $u_0, u_1 \in C(X; U)$ and $x \in X$, $u_0(x) = u_1(x)$ implies $(F(u_0))(x) = (F(u_1))(x)$. So, there exists a function f from $X \times U$ to \mathbb{R} such that for any $u \in C(X; U)$ and $x \in X$, $(F(u))(x) = f(x, u(x))$ holds.

Proof : From

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(u_1) - F(u_0) &= \int_0^1 (F'((1-t)u_0 + tu_1))(u_1 - u_0) dt \\
 &= \int_0^1 (F'((1-t)u_0 + tu_1)) \left(\sum_{k=1}^n (u_1^{(k)} - u_0^{(k)}) e_k \right) dt \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_0^1 (u_1^{(k)} - u_0^{(k)}) (F'((1-t)u_0 + tu_1))(e_k) dt, \\
 &\qquad\qquad\qquad (F(u_1))(x) - (F(u_0))(x) \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_0^1 (u_1^{(k)}(x) - u_0^{(k)}(x)) ((F'((1-t)u_0 + tu_1))(e_k))(x) dt \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_0^1 0 ((F'((1-t)u_0 + tu_1))(e_k))(x) dt = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

holds. ■

2 : I try to define an analog of singular homology theory for a continuous family of topological spaces, but I do not know whether it will work or not.

Let π be a continuous mapping from a topological space M to one X . Let Δ^k denote the standard k -simplex. Let T_k^π be the set of all continuous mappings $\sigma : \Delta^k \times X \rightarrow M$ such that for any $(x, t) \in \Delta^k \times X$,

$$(\pi \circ \sigma)(x, t) = t$$

holds. Then, let S_k^π be the free \mathbb{Z} -module such that T_k^π is a base of S_k^π . In an appropriate class, it appears to be isomorphic to the *usual* singular homology. —

3 : I am considering the following in the interview, but I do not know whether it will work or not. It might be related to a **complex foliation**.

[Title] Dolbeault theorem for a topological sum of complex structures.

[Abstract] For an open set U of $\mathbb{C}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m$, let $O(U)$ denote the ring of all \mathbb{C} -valued continuous functions $f(z, t)$ on U such that $f(z, t)$ is holomorphic with respect to the several complex variables $z \in \mathbb{C}^n$. Then, $\{O(U)\}_U$ is a sheaf of commutative rings on $\mathbb{C}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m$. We show Dolbeault theorem

$$H^q(U, O_U) \cong H_{\partial_z}^q(U, O_U).$$

Further, we show that if D is an open polydisk of \mathbb{C}^n , T is an open set of \mathbb{R}^m and $U = D \times T$ and $q \geq 1$ hold, then this cohomology is vanishing. So, it is shown that for a continuous family of additive Cousin data on an open polydisk, there exists a continuous family of solutions of the first problem.

[Comments] An open set U of $\mathbb{C}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m$ is a very simple example of a continuous sum of \mathbb{C} -manifolds. On the other hand, an appropriate Banach \mathbb{C} -manifold is a continuous product. A projection $\pi : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is a simple example of a continuous family. It seems that a continuous sum and a continuous family have not been fully studied yet. A finite sum and a finite product are familiar, but it seems that a *finite family* is not paying much attention. Although a continuous sum and a continuous family are unexplored places, they may remain unexplored for a while in the future or may be stepped on in a moment.

The $C(X)$ -manifold M corresponding to a continuous family $\pi : U \rightarrow X$ and the total space U do not seem to reflect all of the important structures of π . It is desirable to construct a consistent structure as a whole by adding some additional information to M or U . For example, it seems that the sheaf $\{M|_D\}_D$ on X reflects most information on π . Here, for an open set D of X , $M|_D$ is the $C_b(D)$ -manifold corresponding to $\pi|_D$. —

4 : We try to define the structure sheaf of a manifold that is *locally* a continuous family of \mathbb{C} -manifolds (and also the one of an analytic family).

[Continuous family] Let $\pi : M \rightarrow X$ be a continuous family of \mathbb{C} -manifolds. Then, for an open set U of M , let $O_\pi(U)$ be the set of all pairs (f, g) of \mathbb{C} -valued continuous functions on U such that for any $t \in X$, $f|_{\pi^{-1}(\{t\})}$ is locally constant and $g|_{\pi^{-1}(\{t\})}$ is \mathbb{C} -holomorphic.

[Analytic family] Let $\pi : M \rightarrow X$ be an analytic family of \mathbb{C} -manifolds. Then, for an open set U of M , let $O_\pi(U)$ be the set of all pairs (f, g) of \mathbb{C} -holomorphic functions on U such that for any $t \in X$, $f|_{\pi^{-1}(\{t\})}$ is locally constant. —

5 : A holomorphic vector bundle is a complex one, and a complex one is a real one. So, similarly, define a **complex foliation**. That is, a holomorphic foliation is a complex one, and a complex one is a real one. —

6 : Let $M \rightarrow X$ be an **analytic family** of compact \mathbb{C} -manifolds. Let U be a relatively compact open set of X . Let $\Gamma(M|U)$ denote the set of all continuous sections of M on U . Then, $\Gamma(M|U)$ is a $C_b(U)$ -manifold. (see [8].) In some cases, a **stronger structure** may be introduced into the $C_b(U)$ -manifold. The following problem is related to it. Let $\pi_1 : M \rightarrow X$ and $\pi_2 : M \rightarrow X$ be analytic families. Suppose that X is Stein and $\Gamma(M) \cong (C_b(X))^n$ holds. Then, does $\pi_1 \cong \pi_2$ hold ? (Oka-Grauert principle) —

7 : Let X be a compact Hausdorff space. Then, define a $C(X)$ -analytic set of a Banach $C(X)$ -module. Also, define a $C(X)$ -algebraic set of a finitely generated projective $C(X)$ -module. —

8 : Define a locally direct product space of complex analytic spaces and its underlying complex analytic space. Define a locally direct product space of complex algebraic varieties (or, schemes etc.) and its underlying complex algebraic variety (or, scheme etc.). However, the rudimentary general theory of a ringed space may bring a locally direct product space. On the other hand, an underlying space may be more difficult. —

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